

Preprocessing Plan

Respiratory related signals in EEG

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This document serves to preregister the preprocessing plan of my Master thesis project titled "Respiratory related signals in EEG" which I am conducting at the Translational Neuromodeling Unit (TNU). The goal of this project is to quantify electroencephalography (EEG) responses to natural, unrestricted breathing, or more specifically, to discover and characterize EEG responses that are linked to particular periods of the (physiological) breathing cycle. This may be used as a baseline for experiments in which breathing will be modified to explore interoceptive processing.

In this preprocessing plan, I describe the data set which is studied, how it was split into a discovery and validation subset, and how the validation subset will be preprocessed. The details of the statistical analyses applied to the validation subset will be reported in a separate analysis plan which will be written and preregistered before any statistical analysis will be performed.

Data set

The data set analyzed in this project was collected as part of a previous study by Petzschner et al. [1]. It includes the EEG data of 40 healthy male participants, who performed a heartbeat attention and several other tasks (heartbeat counting, mismatch negativity (MMN), unconstrained cognition or "resting state"). During all tasks, continuous EEG data were recorded at a sampling rate of 500 Hz using a 64-channel EEG cap (BrainCap from BrainVision). In addition to the EEG data, an electrocardiogram (ECG) and pulse oximeter recordings as well as respiratory data using a breathing belt were obtained. The breathing data has not been previously analyzed. All data were recorded both in a "resting state" as well as for a set of tasks, leading to a total of 280 EEG runs (1 resting state run and 6 task-based runs leading to 7 runs per participant) with a recording length between 8 and 21 minutes.

To our knowledge, only few studies [2], [3] have so far looked at the detailed coupling of EEG data with natural, unrestricted breathing in humans. So far, there is neither a clear single hypothesis as to how EEG data may correlate with specific aspects of breathing nor is there a standard preprocessing strategy for EEG data in this context. Thus, to explore multiple paths of analysis without risking to diminish the credibility of our results, the available data were split into two subsets:

- Discovery subset (10 randomly chosen participants with 7 recordings each and all their data points)
- Validation subset (the 30 remaining participants)

After having explored different preprocessing options on the discovery subset, we have decided on the final preprocessing pipeline that will be applied to the validation data set. This document describes the chosen preprocessing pipeline for the validation data set. Please note that at the time of writing this document, the validation data have not yet been touched.

Preprocessing

The data will be preprocessed using MATLAB ¹ and SPM12.

EEG data

The EEG data will be preprocessed in two different ways, depending on the type of the subsequent analysis: analyzing event-related potentials (ERP) or time-frequency based analysis. The two pipelines only differ in the spectral filters which are applied.

First, the continuous EEG recordings will be re-referenced to the average of the two mastoids, which are approximated by the electrodes at locations TP9 and TP10. Next, the data will be high-pass filtered using a fourth-order Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of 0.5 Hz for the ERP analysis and 0.1 Hz for the time-frequency based analysis. This is followed by down-sampling to 250 Hz. For the ERP analysis, a low-pass filter using a fourth-order Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of 30 Hz is applied.

Eye-movement related artifacts

Eye-blink related artifacts will be corrected by using the signal space projection (SSP) method as implemented in SPM12. A detailed description of this procedure can be found in [4].

Part of this eye-blink correction procedure is to visually inspect the spatial topography of the first identified components (using singular value decomposition) as well as the average eye blink in the VEOG and Fp1 channels. These plots are compared to the typical spatial and temporal topography of an eye-blink artifact. If the identified components do not correspond to the typical eye-blink artifact topography, the following procedures may be applied:

- Manually inspecting individual eye-blink trials and excluding incorrectly identified ones
- Inspecting EEG signal quality and excluding noisy channels
- Inspecting EEG signal quality and cropping noisy parts EEG trace

If even after application of these additional measures no component corresponding to the typical spatial and temporal topography of an eye-blink artifact can be identified, the data set is excluded from further analysis.

Breathing belt data

The breathing belt data will be preprocessed such that temporal information about the respiratory cycle can be recovered.

First, the data is cleaned, similarly to the preprocessing reported in [5]: The data will be high-pass filtered using a fourth-order Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of 0.05Hz corresponding to a breathing cycle of 20 s. Next, it is down-sampled to 250 Hz to match the sampling rate of the

¹ Version 24.1.0.2653294 (R2024a) Update 5

preprocessed EEG data. This is followed by a low-pass filter using a fourth-order Butterworth filter with cutoff frequency at 0.5Hz.

To extract the phase of the respiratory cycle, a Hilbert transform will be applied to the breathing signal $s(t)$ to decompose it into an instantaneous magnitude $s_m(t)$ and an instantaneous phase $\phi(t)$:

$$s(t) = s_m(t) \cos(\phi(t)).$$

This instantaneous phase $\phi(t)$ of the respiratory signal will be analyzed in relation to EEG as a continuous signal for the time-frequency based analysis.

For the ERP analysis, the instantaneous phase $\phi(t)$ is used to identify the temporal onsets of individual respiratory cycles as the zero-crossing of $\cos(\phi(t))$. Within each respiratory cycle, the phase time course will be further examined to exclude “unusual” breathing patterns. Breathing cycles that include a reversal of the phase signal at any point within the cycle will be removed from further ERP analysis. If after this removal, less than 50 respiratory cycles remain within a run, the whole run is rejected.

Exclusion criteria

To ensure the data quality, the following criteria will lead to the exclusion of a data set from any subsequent analysis:

- Technical issues during data collection
 - o This led to the exclusion of 0 runs in the discovery set
- Bad EEG signal quality: Failure to identify an eyeblink component with the typical spatial and temporal topography of an eyeblink artifact
 - o This led to the exclusion of 0 runs in the discovery set
- Bad EEG signal quality: More than 3 (5%) bad channels after preprocessing
 - o This led to the exclusion of 0 runs in the discovery set
- Bad breathing signal quality: Failure to extract a cyclical respiratory phase
 - o This led to the exclusion of 1 run in the discovery set
- Bad breathing signal quality: Failure to detect at least 50 respiratory cycles within a run
 - o This led to the exclusion of 2 runs in the discovery set
- In cases where more than 3 (50%) of the runs of the same subject were excluded based on the above criteria, the remaining recordings of the subject are excluded as well
 - o This did not occur in the discovery set

In total, 5 of the 70 runs (less than 10%) in the discovery set were excluded based on the criteria defined above.

References

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